

D1.4

Updated Data Management Plan

Date: 20.06.2025

Version: 1.0

**Funded by
the European Union**

SOIL O-LIVE (Grant Agreement ID: 101091255) is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EIC. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable 1.4 Updated Data Management Plan

Document Information

Project title	SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES
Project acronym	SOIL O-LIVE
Grant Agreement	101091255
Work package	WP1 – Coordination and management
Deliverable number and title	D1.4 Updated Data Management Plan
Deliverable description	Development of an updated Data Management Plan (DMP) for the project. To support EUSO effectively, the consortium will specify relevant knowledge and data sets in the DMPs and designate a contact person to engage in data management discussions with the JRC's EUSO. This revision incorporates key updates derived from directions gathered during the Data & Management Soil Mission Cluster and interactions with the SoilWise project.
Deliverable type	DMP – Data Management Plan
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Lead beneficiary	UJA
Due submission date	30 June 2025 (M30)
Submission date	17.12.2025

Document Author(s) and Reviewer(s)

Name	Entity	Role (author, reviewer)
A.J. Manzaneda Ávila	UJA	Author / reviewer

Document history

Version	Date	Made by	Short Description of Changes
1.0	17.12.2025	A.J. Manzaneda Ávila	Initial version
2.0	20.06.2026	A.J. Manzaneda Ávila	Acknowledgement of EU funding

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an updated version of the Soil O-live project's Data Management Plan (DMP). It aims to analyze the core components of the data management policy applicable across the project, including all datasets created and utilized. The format follows the guidelines for Horizon Europe calls and incorporates suggestions from the Soil Mission Data & Management Cluster meetings and the SoilWise Soil Mission Project to align data sharing with the JRC. Specifically, the DMP maintained its original structure and content, unchanged from earlier DMP versions. Still, this updated version now incorporates the latest Data & Management Cluster and SoilWise recommendations regarding the JRC proposal on metadata template items. Here, we provide a permanent link to the ZENODO repository containing all data and products from the Soil O-live project.

1. Introduction and purpose

This Data Management Plan (DMP) aims to outline how the project's datasets will be managed throughout its duration and after the end of the project. It will cover data standards and metadata, sharing, archiving preservation, and security to ensure proper management principles are followed. This DMP describes how research data was collected, generated, shared, and preserved in the project context and after the end of the project, following FAIR data principles. The data generated by the project through the different work packages (WPs) will primarily be utilized to accomplish the objectives outlined in the project proposal. The project will collect data from innovative observations obtained from laboratory and/or field experiments, surveys, and assays specified in the project. Additionally, if needed, existing data from public repositories, digital archives, and databases, such as geographical, climatic, economic, etc., will be incorporated to complement the project's data analysis. The nature of the SOIL O-LIVE data set is diverse in line with its multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approach. It comprises ecological data (e.g., soil biodiversity, climate, soil physical and chemical properties, land degradation estimates, restoration methodologies, and effectiveness, etc.), agronomic data (e.g., olive yield and quality, land management, tree physiological status, etc.), geographical data (latitude, longitude, elevation, slope, etc.), genomic data (e.g., genetic polymorphisms, genome annotations, genome size, chromosome number, etc.), chemical data (e.g., soil pesticide-toxicity data, soil copper concentration, antibiotic, and microplastic pollution). Lastly, it encompasses socio-economic data such as surveys on sustainability and market trends related to olive oil consumption and health.

The DMP is a public deliverable of the SOIL O-LIVE project. It includes initial, mid-term, and final reports (D1.3, D1.4, and D1.5). Such deliverables will be available (i) at the internal SOIL O-LIVE repository, which constitutes the internal Consortium document and data repository for the project (Google® Drive Tool); and (ii) at the ZENODO platform (https://zenodo.org/communities/soil_o-live/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest). In addition, a permanent link to deliverables is available on the SOIL O-LIVE webpages (<https://soilolive.eu>).

The Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (JRC) and the Soil O-live Consortium have a collaboration agreement. As per this agreement, after the SOIL O-LIVE project ends, they will transfer relevant data, knowledge except, if any of the information has potential value for exploitation, and indicators to the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO) and the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC), except for any personal data collected during the project. For this reason, relevant soil data and information will be available also in the ESAC repository (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/resource-type/datasets>).

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the project's objectives?

SOIL O-LIVE will produce various datasets of different types, including both quantitative and qualitative data. The management of this data will aid in achieving the project's scientific goals and disseminating its results. Two main categories of data management are:

- 1) **Research objectives.** The datasets in this category provide all the necessary data for users to reproduce the scientific results of the project. This encompasses experimental data (including standardized analysis methods and agreed protocols), observations, genome annotations, computer simulations, and data production and analysis codes. Likewise, it includes all relevant metadata necessary for EUSO development and validation of indicators for “Soil health” as listed in the implementation plan of the EU-Soil Mission.
- 2) **Outreach, dissemination, and communications data.** This collection includes preprints, technical reports, conference presentations or abstract, educational resources, and data related to outreach, dissemination, and communications. However, if any of the information has potential value for exploitation, particularly for the new prototype developed by UCLM, it will be protected by patents, copyrights, or other appropriate means.

2. Alignment with Mission Soil Data & Knowledge Management

Participation in the CLUSTER on Data & Knowledge Management meetings (Brussels, 2024, 2025) provided SOIL O-LIVE with strategic guidance on data and knowledge management practices aligned with the objectives of the Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” and relevant EU policy frameworks. Participation of SOIL O-LIVE reinforces the project’s commitment to implementing **FAIR data principles** throughout the project lifecycle. All data and knowledge generated within SOIL O-LIVE will be made **findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable** by ensuring open access publication where possible, comprehensive metadata documentation, clear licensing, version control, and long-term preservation in trusted repositories (e.g., Zenodo).

These meetings identified [SoilWise](#) as the central catalogue for metadata from Mission Soil projects and a key interface with EUSO. In response, SOIL O-LIVE will align its data management workflows with SoilWise requirements by:

- publishing datasets and knowledge outputs in open repositories compatible with SoilWise harvesting;
- applying the agreed metadata templates and standards promoted by the Data & Knowledge Management Cluster;
- using common vocabularies and glossaries where available to support semantic interoperability.

Progress on developing a **soil-specific metadata template** (see Annex II) is particularly relevant to SOIL O-LIVE. The project will adopt this template, once finalized, to complement generic metadata standards and ensure that soil-specific information (e.g., soil properties, indicators, spatial and temporal coverage, methods) is consistently described across project databases, repositories, and EU-level platforms. The meetings also emphasized that data management must extend beyond datasets to include **knowledge products** such as reports, guidelines, software, digital tools, and website content. Accordingly, SOIL O-LIVE will manage these outputs as reusable knowledge assets, supported by structured metadata, persistent identifiers, and long-term accessibility to ensure continued use beyond the project duration.

Finally, the discussions highlighted the importance of **governance, quality assurance, and legacy planning**. In line with these recommendations, SOIL O-LIVE will maintain an up-to-date Data Management Plan (e.g., this deliverable), designate responsibilities for data stewardship within the consortium, and plan for the preservation and accessibility of key data and knowledge assets after project completion.

Through alignment with the Data & Knowledge Management Cluster and SoilWise, SOIL O-LIVE ensures compliance with Horizon Europe Open Science requirements and maximizes the long-term impact, reusability, and policy relevance of its data and knowledge outputs.

3. Type of data

What types and formats of data will the project generate or reuse?

The SOIL O-LIVE project will produce different types of data in various formats. Examples of these types of data, as well as their descriptions, are listed in the table below (Table 1). The sources, formats, and levels of data sharing will be determined based on a survey conducted among the consortium members (see Annex I).

What is the expected data size that you intend to generate or re-use?

Elevated (Terabyte order) in all the cases because of the extent and the temporal frame of the study and the type of data collected.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility') outside your project?

The EU Green Deal for 2030 and related programs require agriculture production to meet certain standards. This makes the data collection particularly valuable for stakeholders in the olive oil sector, such as producers, cooperative managers, regional and national representatives, politicians with agro-environmental responsibilities, and distribution companies. The data will also benefit olive oil producers from other regions who want to implement sustainable practices in their production. Additionally, the data will aid in cultivating other Mediterranean woody crops, like almonds or pistachio, that grow in similar ecological conditions. Finally, data will be very important for the scientific community in several fields of knowledge because the project will provide quality data to answer unsolved questions on agroecology and the sustainability of agriculture.

Table 1.

Type of data	Description	Formats ¹	Source	Dissemination Level/ Data Sharing	Owner or responsible Partner	Licence for the dataset	Archiving and preservation
Geographical (WP1)	Data on the longitude, latitude, elevation, and slope of the 53 orchards selected in the project. It includes metadata with the primary descriptors of the orchards (phytochemical input/hectare/year, orchard size, the density of plantation, age, cultivar type, owner gender, and mode of governance). Land cover and land use data for each orchard is also generated	csv, xml, kml, shp, shx, jpg, pdf, Geotiff	Gathered by the Consortium: In situ collection using a device GPS from the orchard centroid. Gathered by the Consortium: Laboratory validation for polygons and perimeter by using GIS analyses. Digital Elevation Model	Public	UJA	The license used for this dataset: <input type="checkbox"/> CC0 PDDL CC-BY-4.0 ODbL <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: <input type="checkbox"/> CC0 <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	The portion of the data that will be relevant for a publication will be available through the following platform(s) and/or repositories: Zenodo <i>The duration of the preservation will be: N/A</i> <i>Foreseen costs of the preservation: N/A</i> <i>Means to cover preservation costs: N/A</i>
Ecological (WP2-WP3-WP4-WP5-WP6)	<u>Soil Biodiversity</u> : This database contains geo-referenced information about the diversity of soil-living organisms, including bacteria (symbiotic or not), fungi, nematodes, ants, and plant species. It includes taxonomic, functional, and genomic estimates of biodiversity, beta-diversity estimates for different cultivation methods and comparisons of diversity over time and between regions. Additionally, it provides estimates of gamma diversity variation for each region. <u>Soil properties</u> : Geo-referenced data on chemical and physical parameters that it	csv, xml, HTML, GeoTIFF, txt Optical microscopy data (TAR.GZ)	Gathered by the Consortium: In situ collection from soil sampling at study orchards. Metabarcoding and metagenomic data. (BLAST) OTU clustering Functional biodiversity in existing databases				

¹ Putative type of formats.

Type of data	Description	Formats ¹	Source	Dissemination Level/ Data Sharing	Owner or responsible Partner	Licence for the dataset	Archiving and preservation
	<p>includes all soil components of the EU Statistical Office's Land Use and Coverage Area Frame Survey (LUCAS)². Information on two soil horizons, specifically the 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm layers, will be provided separately.</p> <p><u>Climate</u>: Geo-referenced data on precipitation, temperature, and aridity at the scale of 1km</p> <p><u>Soil Restoration</u>: Geo-referenced multivariate data on variation in degraded/polluted soils after restoration amendments</p> <p><u>Ecosystem services</u>: Geo-referenced data on pest abundance (<i>Prays oleae</i> and <i>Bactrocera oleae</i>) and fruit damage. Geo-referenced data on soil gas exchange and water flux. Carbon fixation potential</p>		<p>(e.g., TRY: Plant Trait database, BacDive)</p> <p>Gathered by the Consortium:</p> <p>In situ collection from soil sampling at study orchards.</p> <p>WorldClim, Chelsa Climate, CGIAR</p> <p>Gathered by the Consortium:</p> <p>In situ collection from experimental plots in selected orchards</p> <p>Gathered by the Consortium</p> <p>In situ periodic surveys and experiments</p>				
Pollution³	<u>Pesticides</u> : The data provided is geo-referenced		Gathered by the				

² Orgiazzi, A., Ballabio, C., Panagos, P., Jones, A., & Fernández-Ugalde, O. (2018). LUCAS soil, the largest expandable soil dataset for Europe: A review. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 69(1), 140– 153.

³ Information on two soil horizons, specifically the 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm layers, will be provided separately

Type of data	Description	Formats ¹	Source	Dissemination Level/ Data Sharing	Owner or responsible Partner	Licence for the dataset	Archiving and preservation
(WP2-WP6)	<p>and contains information on the quantity and presence of herbicides, fungicides, and insecticides found in soils and olive oils. It also includes details on the concentration of copper in the soil. Special attention to glyphosate and oxyfluorfen.</p> <p><u>Microplastic</u>: geo-referenced data on the presence and abundance of soil microplastics.</p> <p><u>Nitrogen excess</u>: geo-referenced data on soil Nitrogen concentration.</p> <p><u>Antibiotics</u>: geo-referenced data for the presence of antibiotics and other veterinarian residues in olive orchard soils</p>	<p>csv, xml, GeoTIFF,</p> <p>csv, xml, GeoTiff</p> <p>csv, xml, GeoTiff</p> <p>csv, xml, GeoTiff</p>	<p>Consortium: In situ periodic surveys and experiments</p> <p>Gathered by the Consortium: In situ periodic surveys and experiments</p> <p>Gathered by the Consortium: In situ periodic surveys and experiments</p>				
Agronomical (WP6)	<p><u>Olive oil production and quality</u>: geo-referenced data on the number of kilograms of oil/ha for each orchard. Data on olive oil quality from standardized procedures provided by the International Olive oil Council based on the physico-chemical profile. Qualitative evaluation of olive oil by organoleptic tasting (IOC criteria)</p> <p><u>Tree-Physiology</u>: geo-referenced evaluation of post-summer drought three health in terms of foliar analyses (C/N) and water use efficiency (WUE) from carbon isotopic signatures.</p> <p><u>Digital twin</u></p>	<p>csv, xml, GeoTiff</p> <p>csv, xml, GeoTiff</p>	<p>Gathered by the Consortium: In situ sample collection of olive and oils</p> <p>International Tasting Panel</p> <p>In situ sample collection of leaves</p> <p>Remote sensing data</p>				

Type of data	Description	Formats ¹	Source	Dissemination Level/ Data Sharing	Owner or responsible Partner	Licence for the dataset	Archiving and preservation
Land degradation (WP3)	<u>Soil erosion indicators.</u> <u>Soil erosion and degradation modelling</u>	csv, xml, GeoTiff	Gathered by the Consortium: In situ data collection Remote mapping (Copernicus monitoring data and infrastructures) Modelling outcomes Isotopic signatures		Università RomaTre & University of Basel	CC-BY-4.0	All data supporting the findings of the WP3 research activity will be made available in ZENODO and, if applicable, at the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC), the institutional soil data repository of the European Commission Joint Research Centre.
Genomic and genetic (WP5)	<u>Plant DNA C-values and chromosome number data</u> <u>Genome assemblies, gene annotation based on RNAseq, genomic diversity (GBS/ddRAD) data.</u>	csv, xml, GeoTiff, jpg (Fluorescence intensity graphs) FASTQ, FASTA, GFF, VCF	Gathered by the Consortium: in situ sampling collection and laboratory flow cytometry in situ sampling collection and nucleotide sequencing				
Social Surveys and dissemination & communication (WP7)	<u>Survey data:</u> data from surveys on sustainability practices conducted on farmer populations at regional level. Gender studies in olive farming <u>Dissemination and Communication data:</u> Presentations or abstract in international/national conferences for expert audiences, outreach talks, teaching materials (including scientific papers, talk presentations,	csv, xml PDF, Keynote, PPT, JPG, mp4	in situ sampling collection Consortium elaboration				

Type of data	Description	Formats ¹	Source	Dissemination Level/ Data Sharing	Owner or responsible Partner	Licence for the dataset	Archiving and preservation
	videos, and posters)						

4. FAIR data

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

The data will be identified through Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and INSDC accessions provided by Zenodo repository where data will be stored (see below).

PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

Each data set will have specific metadata standards; examples of metadata are summarized in the table below. Procedures to generate metadata are given in the **Deliverable 7.1 (D7.1)**.

Table 2.

Type of data	Metadata format	Elements	License
Biodiversity and Taxonomy	GBIF ⁴	Title, description, creator, contact information, license, dataset ID, geographic coverage, taxonomic coverage, temporal coverage, data quality, data format, data access details, and citation.	Creative Commons Attribution-NonComercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International
Ecological including land degradation	Ecological Metadata Language (EML)	Title, abstract, creator, temporal and spatial coverage, keywords, methods, variables, data quality, publications, data access, and usage.	Creative Commons Attribution-NonComercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International
Pollution	Ecological Metadata Language (EML)	Title, abstract, creator, temporal and spatial coverage, keywords, methods, variables, data quality, publications, data access, and usage.	Creative Commons Attribution-NonComercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International CC-BY-NC-4.0 ODbL
Agriculture	AGRIS ⁵	Title, alternative title, creator: personal, corporate and conference, publisher, place of publication, date of publication, subject: classification and thesaurus, description: notes, edition, abstract, identifier, type, format, language relation, availability source coverage: spatial, temporal rights: statement, terms of use citation: title, identifier, number, chronology	Creative Commons Attribution-NonComercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International
Genomic and genetic	Sequence Read Archive (SRA) ⁶ , BioSamples ⁷ , European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) ⁸ , European Variation Archive	Study (title, description, principal investigators, affiliations, and funding sources), Experiment (experimental design, sample attributes, library preparation methods, sequencing platforms used, and any relevant protocols followed), Sample (sample name or ID, organism name, strain, tissue type, disease status, and other relevant	EMBL-EBI will minimise barriers to reuse of data in EMBL-EBI resources by adopting the Creative Commons (CC) license framework across all its data resources in the next 5 years. [2023,

⁴ Global Biodiversity Information Facility (<https://www.gbif.org/>).

⁵ <https://www.fao.org/3/ae909e/ae909e00.htm>

⁶ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>

⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples>

⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>

Type of data	Metadata format	Elements	License
	(EVA) ⁹	annotations). Run: (sequencing platform used, sequencing file format, read length, number of reads, and any associated quality control measures), Data Processing (data processing steps and bioinformatics pipelines applied to the raw sequencing data, alignment, variant calling, quality control), Data Availability, Experimental Factors, Data Quality.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/licencing/
Flow cytometry	MIFlowCyt ¹⁰	Experimental Overview (experimental design, sample types, and any controls or standards used), Instrument Description (instrument manufacturer, model, configuration, and settings such as laser excitation wavelengths and detection channels), Sample Preparation (sample handling, preparation, and staining protocols, sample source, cell types, labelling reagents, staining procedures, and any treatments or manipulations performed), Data Acquisition (acquisition parameters, settings, gating strategies, compensation matrices, and any data pre-processing steps applied during acquisition). Data Analysis (gating strategies, data transformation, statistical analysis, and any specific algorithms or software used for data processing and visualization. Results, Standardization and Quality Control	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International
Social surveys	DDI ¹¹	Study Description, Documentation (protocols, data collection manuals, codebooks, questionnaires, and any other relevant documents that provide additional information about the study design and data collection procedures), data collection (sample size, data collection mode, data collection timeline, and any training provided to interviewers or survey administrators), data variables, data structure, data quality, data access and use conditions, and publications	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International

4.2. Making data accessible

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

The official repository for data and software codes generated by the Soil O-live project is located on **ZENODO** (https://zenodo.org/communities/soil_o-live/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest), stored in an open file format and with a persistent identifier (DOI) under an open license. Final data, knowledge except, if any of the information has potential value for exploitation, and indicators will also be available on the ESAC

⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/eva>

¹⁰ <http://flowrepository.org/>

¹¹ <https://ddialliance.org/>

repository through a direct link from the Soil O-live web pages. Samples, raw reads, assembled transcripts, and genome assemblies will be submitted to BioSamples and the European

Nucleotide Archive. VCF files containing variation data mapped to reference sequences will be submitted to the European Variation Archive. In collaboration with Ensembl, the genome data and the mapped variants will be available, together with regularly updated comparative genomics data, in the Ensembl genome browsers. The Soil O-live proposal for collaboration in genomic bioinformatic analyses and the development of open genomic data resources has been explicitly endorsed by EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

If deemed to have potential exploitation value (especially for the novel, cutting-edge prototype built by UCLM), the knowledge generated will be protected by patents, copyright, or other means wherever appropriate.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

The data access will be free of restrictions, but respecting at all times the specific licenses of each dataset.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Source code and documentation for data analyses (in languages such as R, Python, etc.) will be available in Zenodo and other specific repositories such as Github, CRAN, etc.

4.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?

See table 2.

Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Here we provide five ways to improve the quality and interoperability of Soil O-live data:

1. Use standardized data formats (refer to Table 1).
2. Comply with metadata standards (refer to Table 2).
3. Use standardized identifiers, such as DOI for scholarly publications and datasets or ORCID for researcher identification. This enables the unique and persistent identification of resources and individuals.

4. Adopt linked data principles based on Uniform Resource Identifier (URI). This allows for the interconnection and integration of diverse datasets across the web, enabling data discovery, exploration, and aggregation.

5. Open Standards and Open Data: Embracing open standards and open data practices promotes interoperability by removing barriers to data access, encouraging data sharing, and enabling collaboration among different stakeholders.

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g., other data from your project)?

Yes, it is absolutely necessary to accomplish the SEM model stated in the proposal. Please refer to Figures 4 and 5 in the GA for more information.

4.4. Increase data re-use

How will you provide the documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

The Soil O-live project's methods, procedures, and protocols are available to the public, and they will be accessible through the project's webpage, which will link to permanent repositories (e.g., Zenodo).

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

The data will be freely available for the public by using a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International license.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes, if open dataset-specific licences are respected at all times.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes (explained in Table 2).

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Key data quality assurance processes:

1. Data Collection Process:

- The data collection process at Soil O-live follows reliable and standardized methods, protocols, and guidelines that have undergone evaluation and agreement. Any consortium member can access these standardized protocols and are open for discussion should any issues arise during sampling. Protocols are revised in each semestral in the ordinary consortium meetings.

- The chosen teams of the consortium have the necessary skills to carry out all the proposed samplings and surveys using common protocols. However, training sessions will be provided for certain tasks, such as the ant taxonomy workshops in September 2023. These workshops aim to ensure accurate taxa classification.

2. Data Validation and Cleaning:

- Before any analysis, the person in charge of gathering data, under the supervision of task leaders, thoroughly reviews all data sets to check for errors, inconsistencies, and outliers. The consortium member can access and review their own data anytime to detect inconsistencies or errors. To clean and correct data, we use procedures such as removing duplicates, handling missing values, and resolving discrepancies. A general supervision will be performed by the responsible for task 7.1 (Data communication and interoperability assurance) and task 7.2 (Standardization activities)

3. Data Documentation and Metadata:

- The task leader's responsibilities include validating the dataset, creating and maintaining metadata, and preparing all necessary documentation according to the standards in Table 2. Taskleaders will oversee documentation and metadata quality control, ensuring data integrity through range checks, consistency checks, and logical validations. WP leaders will communicate with task leaders to resolve inconsistencies in case of discrepancies or errors. A general supervision will be performed by the responsible for tasks 7.1 (Data communication and interoperability assurance) and 7.2 (Standardization activities).

4. Regular Audits and Reviews:

- Regular audits or reviews of the data quality assurance procedures will be performed by tasks leaders to monitor and evaluate data quality to identify areas for improvement and maintain data integrity. A general supervision will be performed by the responsible for task 7.1 (Data communication and interoperability assurance) and task 7.2 (Standardization activities)

5. Other research outputs

Other research outputs expected throughout Soil O-live project are:

- Agreed Protocols, guidelines, and procedures will be managed similarly – in line with the FAIR principles – as the data detailed in this document.
- Prototype for the chemical restoration of polluted soils in olive groves.

(Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles).

6. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

Soil O-live will use OpenAIRE's permanent open scholarly communication infrastructure, including storage and archiving (e.g, Zenodo). This implies that data storage and archiving will be free of charge. To ensure security, we will use external hard drives as a backup. We will purchase these devices using funds allocated for small equipment items. Additional virtual space may be acquired if necessary for data backup.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Soil O-live coordinator assisted by the whole consortium members.

How will long-term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept, and for how long).

Data will be stored and preserved permanently in the repositories such as Zenodo.

7. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

We will perform data backup weekly through two methods: (i) using an external hard drive device and (ii) creating backup copies of data in virtual spaces like Google Drive®. UJA, our coordinator institution, already has free institutional accounts on Google Drive® with several spaces for data archiving (200 Gb each). Each Task leader will also create additional data backups locally for added security.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes.

8. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and the ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

N/A

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Yes.

9. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

N/A.

ANNEX I

DATA COLLECTION TEMPLATE (one sheet for type of data)

Partner:
TYPE OF DATA:
DATA DESCRIPTION:
Relationship to WP and Tasks:
Source (observational, experimental, simulation, pre-existing data, etc.)
Form and format of the data (text, numeric, audio-visual, computer-software codes, instrument-specific, etc.):
Software/Program to read the data:
Size of the data (and estimation of the extension in bytes along the project):
Metadata standard (see Annex II)
Keywords:
Dissemination Level / Data Sharing (public, private, embargo):
License for the dataset (CC0, PDDL, CC-BY-4.0, ODbL, Other):

Other research outputs (software, code, protocols, new materials, samples):
Funding for data management:
Data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data):
Ethics aspects:
Other aspects (use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management):

ANNEX II

JRC proposal on metadata template items

Id	Proposed Name	Proposed Description	Format of the field
1	Identifier	Unique identification of the dataset. Use a persistent identifier such as DOI. Otherwise, provide an internal UUID.	URL
2	Project Affiliation	Name or identifier (URI) of the project under which the dataset was created. Preferably, it is recommended to use the project DOI.	Free text
3	Mission Soil Affiliation	Field indicating whether the dataset is part of the Mission Soil initiative.	Check box / Boolean
4	Title	A human-readable name for the dataset.	Free text
5	Description	A brief description of the dataset. Should summarize the dataset's content, purpose, methodology, soil properties, and temporal/geographic coverage.	Free text
6	Keywords	Words or phrases describing the dataset's main themes. Select terms from established vocabularies (e.g. GEMET, INSPIRE themes, AGROVOC etc.).	Tagging component / dropdown using different vocabularies
7	File Format	Specify the data format(s) in which the dataset is provided (e.g. CSV, TIFF, Shapefile, NetCDF).	Dropdown from the most common data types
8	Geographic Extent	Spatial coverage of the dataset (e.g. EU, specific country, or NUTS region). For custom extents, provide textual description or bounding box.	Dropdown from list of geographic extent: EU, EU & UK, NUTS
9	Temporal Reference	Date or period to which the dataset refers. Use ISO 8601 format. If relevant, indicate date type (creation / observation / revision).	Date input / date picker
10	Access constraints	Restrictions on obtaining the dataset.	Dropdown (e.g. open, restricted, conditional, metadata only)
11	Use constraints	Conditions governing the use and distribution of the dataset.	Dropdown
12	Contact	Person or organisation to contact regarding the dataset.	Free text
13	Related Resource	A related dataset, publication, or knowledge resource that is associated with the described dataset. This may include input or reference data used in its creation, publications describing the dataset, or other related outputs. When possible,	Free text or URL

Id	Proposed Name	Proposed Description	Format of the field
		provide a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI, URI). If not available, provide a formal citation or descriptive title.	
14	Processing steps	Information about events in the life of a dataset, such as methods applied in data acquisition and processing. Reference standards where possible (e.g. ISO, FAO, LUCAS).	Free text
15	Language	Language(s) of the dataset content or metadata. Specify using ISO 639 codes.	Dropdown (if necessary)
16	Coordinate Reference System	The spatial reference system used to define the coordinate space of the dataset. Provide the.opengis link (e.g. http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326).	Dropdown
17	Citation	Formal citation or bibliographic reference for the dataset or its main source, including authors, year, title, version, and DOI if available.	Free text or URL
18	Spatial Resolution	The level of detail of the data (raster resolution or equivalent scale).	Free text
19	Resource Location	The online location or access point where the resource can be accessed or downloaded. Provide a valid and persistent URL or URI that leads directly to the data file, web service (e.g. WFS, WMS), or a landing page where the resource is available.	URL
20	Soil Properties	Soil properties described in this dataset. Select one or more terms from controlled EUSO vocabularies describing the dataset's thematic focus.	Dropdown from a selection provided by EUSO
21	Soil Function	Soil functions described in this dataset. Select one or more terms from controlled EUSO vocabularies describing the dataset's thematic focus.	Dropdown from a selection provided by EUSO
22	Soil Threats	Soil threats described in this dataset. Select one or more terms from controlled EUSO vocabularies describing the dataset's thematic focus.	Dropdown from a selection provided by EUSO
23	Soil Indicators	Soil indicators described in this dataset. Select one or more terms from controlled EUSO vocabularies describing the dataset's thematic focus.	Dropdown from a selection provided by EUSO